

Synthesis and anthelmintic activity studies of 1-substituted benzimidazole derivatives

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Abstract : A new series of benzimidazoles were prepared by treating *o*-phenylenediamine and formic acid under reflux conditions. Further 1-substituted derivatives of benzimidazoles were synthesized by reaction with chloroacetic acid followed by condensation with amino containing compounds. The structural elucidation of the compounds was performed by FT-IR, ¹H NMR and Mass spectroscopy. The synthesized compounds were subjected to anthelmintic activity studies against *Eudrilus* species. The title compounds exhibited moderate to good anthelmintic activity.

Keywords : Benzimidazoles, chloroacetic acid, anthelmintic activity.

Introduction

Benzimidazole derivatives are of wide interest because of their good clinical application and biological activity. They showed a variety of pharmacological activities like anticancer, anti-HIV¹, antiprotozoal^{2,3}, antiamebic⁴, antifungal^{5,6}, antibacterial⁷, antiviral⁸, anthelmintic⁹, antioxidant¹⁰, gamma aminobutyric acid agonists¹¹ and 5HT₃-antagonists¹². Substituted benzimidazole derivatives have found wide application in veterinary medicine as anthelmintic agents and also in human therapeutic areas such as treatment of ulcers and as antihistamines¹².

Materials and methods :

All the reagents and chemicals were obtained from Avra Chemicals Ltd. and were used without further purification. Melting points were determined in open capillary tubes and were uncorrected. Completion of reaction and purity of compounds were checked by thin layer chromatography (TLC). IR spectra were recorded on FTIR spectrometer using a thin film support on KBr pellets. The values are reported as ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹). ¹H NMR spectra was recorded on Bruker (400 MHz) NMR spectrometer. The spectra was obtained in CDCl₃ and the chemical shift values are reported as values in ppm relative to

TMS ($\delta = 0$) as internal standard. FAB Mass spectra were recorded.

Experimental

Step 1 : Synthesis of benzimidazole (1) :

Mixture of *o*-phenylene diamine (50 mmol) and formic acid (25 mmol) were added to a round bottomed flask and refluxed for 4 h. 20 ml of water was added to the reaction mixture and basified with 10% NaOH solution. The product was filtered, washed several times with water and dried. The completion of reaction was checked by TLC.

Step 2 : Synthesis of acid intermediate (2) :

(a) To the above obtained benzimidazole **1** (50 mmol), chloroacetic acid (51 mmol), dimethyl formamide (DMF) (15 ml) and triethylamine (TEA) (4 ml) were added and refluxed for 4 h. The solvent was removed by evaporation to give the crude product. The completion of reaction was checked by TLC.

(b) Procedure (a) was repeated, only instead of DMF and TEA, chloroform (CHCl₃) and pyridine were used.

Step 3 : Condensation of acid intermediate with amine compounds (3a, 3b) :

To the above obtained acid intermediate, DMF (20

ml) and TEA (7.5 mmol) were added and stirred for 15 min. After this carbonyl diimidazole (CDI) (3.3 mmol) and 4-chloroaniline/*p*-toluidine (3.3 mmol) were added and stirring was continued for 24 h. Water was added to dissolve DMF and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid. The mixture was then extracted with ethyl acetate and the solvent was evaporated to get the crude product. The completion of reaction was checked by TLC. Using these conditions the following compounds were synthesised

The scheme of reaction for the synthesis of 1-substituted benzimidazoles is shown in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1. Scheme for the synthesis of 1-substituted benzimidazoles.

Anthelmintic activity :

Anthelmintic activity study was carried out against earthworms (*Eudrilus eugeniae*) by modified Garg's method^{13,14}. Suspension of the samples were prepared by triturating the sample with 15% Tween 80 and distilled water and the mixture was stirred using a magnetic stirrer for 30 min. The resulting suspension was used for the activity studies. The suspension was diluted to con-

tain 100 mg in 20 ml of the test sample. The standard drug, mebendazole was also prepared with the same concentration in a similar way. Earthworms were placed in three petri-dishes containing 20 ml of each sample, standard drug and control (20 ml suspension of distilled water and 15% Tween 80) respectively at room temperature. The time required for the paralysis and death of the earthworms were noted. The death time was ascertained by placing the earthworms in warm water at 50 °C, which stimulated the movement if the earthworms were alive.

Results and discussion

The results of the final compounds and the intermediates along with the physical properties are shown in Table 1.

Spectral data :

1*H*-Benzimidazole (1) : IR (KBr pellets) : 3456 (N-H stretch), 1363 (C-N stretch), 1587 (aromatic C=C stretch), 3113 (aromatic C-H stretch) cm⁻¹.

Table 1. Synthesis of 1-substituted benzimidazoles

Sl. No.	Compd.	Physical state	Reaction time (h)	Melting point (°C)	Percentage yield (%)
1.	1	Pink solid	4	166–168	80
2.	2^a	Brown semisolid	6	–	46
3.	2^b	Brown solid	4	68–71	86
4.	3a	Cream solid	24	120–121	25
5.	3b	Brown solid	24	70–72	75

^aChloroacetic acid, DMF, TEA; ^bchloroacetic acid, CHCl₃, pyridine.

1*H*-Benzimidazol-1-ylacetic acid (**2b**) : IR (KBr pellets) : 1631 (C=O stretch), 1240 (C-O stretch), 3427 (O-H stretch), 1305 (C-N stretch), 1485 (aromatic C=C stretch), 2852 (aromatic C-H stretch) cm⁻¹.

2-(1*H*-Benzimidazol-1-yl)-*N*-(4-chlorophenyl)acetamide (**3b**) : IR (KBr pellets) : 1641.4 (C=O stretch), 3454 (N-H stretch), 1566 (C=C stretch), 3115 (aromatic C-H stretch), 1384 (C-N stretch), 2920 (aliphatic C-H stretch) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : 8.6–8.7 (1H, s, -CONH), 7.0–7.4 (8H, m, Ar-H), 2.5–2.8 (1H, s, -N=CH), 2.3 (2H, s, -CH₂-), 2–2.2 (1H, s, Ar-CH₃); FAB Mass : 264.8.

Anthelmintic activity :

The synthesized compounds have shown potent anthelmintic activity as compared to the standard drug, mebendazole. Table 2 illustrates a significant anthelmintic activity of sample and standards.

Table 2. Anthelmintic activity

Sl. No.	Compd.	Concentration (mg)	Paralysis time (min)	Death time (min)
1.	Control	–	–	–
2.	Mebendazole	100	53.5	55.4
3.	1	100	60.2	62.4
4.	2	100	58.6	60.2
5.	3a	100	62.6	64.1
6.	3b	100	52.4	54.6

Conclusion

A simple and efficient scheme for the synthesis of benzimidazole (**1**) and 1-substituted benzimidazoles (**3a,3b**) was developed. The newly synthesised compounds were characterized by FT-IR, ¹H NMR and Mass spectroscopic data. The compounds were evaluated for their anthelmintic activity. All the compounds exhibited moderate ac-

tivity, compound **3b**, which has a *p*-tolyl substituent, showed better activity as compared to the standard drug mebendazole.

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